

1 **Presence of diphenyl phosphate and aryl-phosphate flame retardants in indoor dust**
2 **from different microenvironments in Spain and the Netherlands and estimation of**
3 **human exposure**

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5 Maria K. Björnsdotter^a, Encarnación Romera-García^a, Josep Borrull^b, Jacob de Boer^b,
6 Soledad Rubio^a, Ana Ballesteros-Gómez^{a*}

7

8 ^aDepartment of Analytical Chemistry, Institute of Fine Chemistry and Nanochemistry, Marie
9 Curie Building (Annex), Campus of Rabanales, University of Córdoba, 14071, Spain

10 ^bVrije Universiteit Amsterdam, Environment and Health, De Boelelaan 1087, 1081 HV
11 Amsterdam, the Netherlands.

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13

14 **Corresponding author*

15 E-mail: a02bagoa@uco.es

16 Tel: +34957218643

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24 **Abstract**

25 Phosphate flame retardants (PFRs) are ubiquitous chemicals in the indoor environment.
26 Diphenyl phosphate (DPHP) is a major metabolite and a common biomarker of aryl-PFRs.
27 Since it is used as a chemical additive and it is a common impurity of aryl-PFRs as well as a
28 degradation product, its presence in indoor dust as an additional source of exposure should
29 not be easily ruled out. In this study, DPHP (and TPHP) are measured in indoor dust in
30 samples collected in Spain and in the Netherlands ($n=80$). Additionally, the presence of other
31 emerging aryl-PFRs was monitored by target screening. TPHP and DPHP were present in all
32 samples in the ranges 169-142,459 ng/g and 106-79,661 ng/g, respectively. DPHP
33 concentrations were strongly correlated to the TPHP levels ($r=0.90$, $p<0.01$), suggesting that
34 DPHP could be present as degradation product of TPHP or other aryl-PFRs. Estimated
35 exposures for adults and toddlers in Spain to TPHP and DPHP via dust ingestion (country for
36 which the number of samples was higher) were much lower than the estimated reference dose
37 (US EPA) for TPHP. However, other routes of exposure may contribute to the overall
38 internal exposure (diet, dermal contact with dust/consumer products and inhalation of indoor
39 air). The estimated urinary DPHP levels for adults and toddlers in Spain (0.002-0.032 ng/mL)
40 as a result of dust ingestion were low in comparison with the reported levels, indicating a low
41 contribution of this source of contamination to the overall DPHP exposure. Other aryl-PFRs,
42 namely cresyl diphenyl phosphate (CDP), resorcinol bis(diphenyl phosphate) (RDP), 2-
43 ethylhexyl diphenyl phosphate (EDPHP), isodecyl diphenyl phosphate (IDP) and bisphenol A
44 bis(diphenyl phosphate) (BDP), were all detected in indoor dust, however, with lower
45 frequency.

46 **Keywords:** Aryl-phosphate flame retardants; Indoor dust; Human exposure; Triphenyl
47 phosphate; Diphenyl phosphate

48 1. Introduction

49 Due to their wide use in materials, such as furniture, electronics and textiles, flame
50 retardants (FRs) are widespread in the environment. They are used to prevent ignition and to
51 slow down the spread of an already initiated fire.¹ Concern has been raised considering their
52 migration from materials as it affects the indoor air quality and being inhalation a route for
53 human exposure.² The use of PBDEs as flame retardants has been common until they started
54 to be banned or voluntarily phased-out in certain products, such as electrical and electronic
55 equipment or polyurethane foam, due to their known toxicity, persistence and
56 bioaccumulative properties.³ The European Union has banned the use of pentaBDE and
57 octaBDE in 2004 (Directive 2002/96/EC) and the use of decaBDE in electric and electronic
58 equipment in 2009 (European Court of Justice, 2008). This regulation has led to the
59 introduction of alternatives, such as aryl-phosphate flame retardants (aryl-PFRs), onto the
60 market. Studies have demonstrated an increase in the presence of alternative FRs in indoor
61 dust, for which toxicity is still uncharacterized, in conjunction with the decrease of PBDE.⁴⁻⁶

62 Triphenyl phosphate (TPHP; CAS no. 115-86-6) is an aryl-PFR mainly used as an additive in
63 polymer mixtures used in electronic enclosure applications. The use of TPHP has resulted in
64 environmental contamination due to its migration from materials.² TPHP has been reported in
65 indoor dust collected from the floors of residences (<2-1,798,000 ng/g),^{4, 8-34} in indoor dust
66 from offices (11-50000 ng/g)^{11, 18, 24, 30-34} and in indoor dust from schools and daycare centers
67 (10-90000 ng/g).^{11, 21, 24, 26, 30, 33, 35} TPHP has also been reported in dust from cars (<2-170,000
68 ng/g),^{16, 18, 20, 24, 28, 31} and from public microenvironments (PMEs) such as shops, restaurants
69 and supermarkets (14-34200 ng/g).^{12, 14, 18, 30, 32} TPHP has also been reported in indoor air
70 (0.19-5.7 ng/m³),^{36, 37} in outdoor air (0.003 ng/m³),³⁸ sewage water influent (76-290 ng/L) and
71 effluent (41-130 ng/L) and sewage sludge (52-320 ng/g dw),³⁹ surface water (<LOD-10.3
72 ng/L),⁴⁰ sediment (5.6-253 ng/g)^{41, 42} and in fish (43-230 ng/g lw).^{41, 43} Furthermore, TPHP

73 has been associated with airborne particles over the oceans indicating a potential for long-
74 range atmospheric transport towards the polar regions.⁴⁴

75 The widespread occurrence of TPHP in the indoor- and outdoor environment has led to
76 concern regarding human health and the environment. The human toxicity of TPHP is
77 considered “low to high” according to a recent alternatives assessment report.⁴⁵ Furthermore,
78 PFRs including TPHP may be associated with altered hormone levels and decreased semen
79 quality in men.⁴⁶ The aquatic toxicity is considered very high (Fish 96 h EC₅₀=0.4 mg/L, fish
80 30-day LOEC=0.037 mg/L) and TPHP may cause long-term adverse effects in the aquatic
81 environment.⁴⁵ The environmental persistence is considered low, although there is a moderate
82 potential for bioaccumulation.⁴⁵

83 Human exposure to FRs as well as to other contaminants has been associated with inhalation
84 and ingestion of contaminated indoor dust.⁴⁷ High levels of contaminants in indoor dust are
85 posing a risk to human health, particularly vulnerable groups such as toddlers, which are
86 especially exposed to contaminated dust when crawling and playing on the floor as well as
87 when they put items in their mouth.⁴⁸

88 As a major metabolite of aryl-PFRs, DPHP has been used as a biomarker for assessing
89 exposure to TPHP in indoor dust and has been widely reported in urine in the range <0.13-
90 727 ng/mL.^{25, 49-54} However, the urinary levels of DPHP are not correlated to TPHP
91 concentrations in indoor dust ($r_s=0.04$,⁵⁰ ; $r_s=0.15$,²⁵) indicating other exposure routes. A
92 possible additional source could be the direct exposure to DPHP itself as it is used in other
93 applications (e.g. DPHP is used as a catalyst in polymerization processes^{55,56} and as an
94 additive in paints and coatings according to PubChem database) or direct exposure to DPHP
95 via indoor dust ingestion as it may be present as an impurity and/or as a degradation product
96 as a result of spontaneous or microbial hydrolysis of TPHP and/or of other aryl-PFRs.
97 Furthermore, DPHP has been reported to be a metabolite of some other aryl-PFRs, such as 2-

98 ethylhexyl diphenyl phosphate (EDPHP),^{57,58} resorcinol bis(diphenyl phosphate) (RDP)⁵⁹
99 and *tert*-Butylphenyl diphenyl phosphate (BPDP).⁶⁰ There is almost no data available about
100 the presence of DPHP in the indoor environment, to the best of our knowledge only one study
101 has reported levels of DPHP (75-190 ng/g) in 4 dust samples collected in Australia.⁵³

102 In the present study, TPHP and DPHP levels were studied in indoor dust samples collected
103 from households, offices, cars and public microenvironments in the Netherlands in June 2016
104 ($n=23$) and in Spain in March and April 2017 ($n=57$). The levels of TPHP and DPHP were
105 compared between different microenvironments and between the two countries and the
106 correlation between TPHP and DPHP levels was investigated. Human exposure to TPHP and
107 DPHP via indoor dust ingestion was estimated using different exposure scenarios. It should
108 be taken into account that this is only one of the major identified exposure routes to flame
109 retardants, which include also the diet, dermal contact with dust/consumer products and
110 inhalation of indoor air.

111 Furthermore, to gain knowledge about the presence of other aryl-PFRs in indoor dust, which
112 could contribute to the formation of DPHP, the presence of other emerging aryl-PFRs were
113 screened, namely cresyl diphenyl phosphate (CDP), RDP, EDPHP, isodecyl diphenyl
114 phosphate (IDP) and bisphenol A bis(diphenyl phosphate) (BDP) by injection of authentic
115 standards.

116 **2. Materials and methods**

117 **2.1. Chemicals and reagents**

118 Acetonitrile and methanol were acquired from VWR chemicals (Llinars del Vallès,
119 Barcelona, Spain). Ammonium acetate was obtained from Sigma Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, the
120 Netherlands). Ultra-high-quality water was obtained from a Milli-Q water purification system
121 (Millipore, Madrid, Spain). Standard reference material (SRM) 2585 (organic contaminants

122 in house dust) was provided by the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST).
123 TPHP, DPHP, TPHP-d₁₅ and DPHP-d₁₀ were obtained from Sigma Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, the
124 Netherlands). Cresyl diphenyl phosphate (CDP), isodecyl diphenyl phosphate (IDP), 2-
125 ethylhexyl diphenyl phosphate (EDPHP), resorcinol bis(diphenyl phosphate) (RDP) and
126 bisphenol A bis(diphenyl phosphate) (BDP) analytical standards were obtained from
127 AccuStandard (New Haven, CT).

128 **2.2. Sample collection**

129 Sampling was performed using a filter (40 µm) mounted in a nozzle adapted to a vacuum
130 cleaner and samples were not further sieved. Dust samples were collected from residences in
131 the Netherlands in June 2016 from floors (*n*=12) and from the surface of electrical equipment
132 (*n*=11) and in Spain in March and April 2017 from the floors of living rooms (*n*=9),
133 bedrooms (*n*=9), offices (*n*=4), surfaces of electrical equipment (*n*=13), cars (*n*=15) and
134 public microenvironments (PMEs) (*n*=7) (two electronic shops, two clothing shops, one sport
135 clothing shop, one decoration shop and one cafeteria). Due to the limited amount of dust on
136 top of electrical equipment, these samples were of approximately 20-50 mg.

137 **2.3. Sample treatment and method validation**

138 Approximately 50 mg dust (except for dust on top of electronic equipment, 20-50 mg)
139 were accurately weighed in 15 mL glass tubes and spiked with IS (TPHP-d₁₅ and DPHP-d₁₀,
140 0.1 µg each) prior to extraction. Salting-out extraction with acetonitrile was performed with 3
141 M aqueous ammonium acetate (NH₄Ac):acetonitrile (1:1 v/v) by vortex for 2 min followed
142 by centrifugation at 3000 rpm for 5 min. After phase-separation, the acetonitrile layer was
143 collected and transferred to a glass tube. The extraction was repeated 2 times and the
144 acetonitrile layers (~ 6 mL) were combined and evaporated to approximately 1.5 mL (N₂,
145 50°C). Sample clean-up was performed with dispersive SPE (75 mg MgSO₄, 25 mg PSA, 25

146 mg C₁₈, 25 mg GCB) by vortex for 2 min followed by ultracentrifugation at 10 000 rpm for 5
147 min. The extract was then evaporated to near dryness (N₂, 50°C) and reconstituted in 200 µL
148 MilliQ water:acetonitrile (1:1 v/v) by vortex for 30 s followed by ultracentrifugation at
149 10,000 rpm for 5 min. Extracts were transferred to LC vials and aliquots of 5 µL were
150 injected into the LC-MS/MS system.

151 Procedural blanks were included in each set of experiments and used for data treatment to
152 correct for possible blank contamination. Blank values for DPHP and TPHP (average, n=10)
153 were of 10±2 ng/g for TPHP and 5±1 ng/g for DPHP (detectable but far below the estimated
154 method LOQ).

155 The analytical performance of the method was evaluated for extraction recovery (%), clean-
156 up recoveries (%), matrix effects (%), and reproducibility (RSD%) by using the indoor dust
157 reference material SRM 2585 (50 mg).

158 **2.4. Apparatus and sample analysis**

159 For separation, an Agilent Technologies 1200 LC system was used with a Phenomenex
160 Luna® C₁₈ column (2.0 mm i.d., 100 mm length, 3.0 µm particle size). The mobile phase
161 consisted of 5 mM aqueous ammonium acetate (A) and methanol (B) at a flow rate of 0.25
162 mL/min. The gradient was as follows: initial 20% B, increased to 95% in 7.5 min and hold
163 for 3 min and finally re-conditioning for 7 min. The MS/MS system was an Agilent
164 Technologies 6420 Triple Quadrupole mass spectrometer equipped with LC-electrospray
165 ionization (ESI) source. The source parameters were set as following: Gas temperature,
166 320°C; gas flow, 12.0 L/min; nebulizer, 50 psi; capillary voltage, +/-4000 V; MS1 heater,
167 100°C; MS2 heater, 100°C. The MRM transitions for target masses are given in Table S-1.
168 TPHP, BADP, RDP, IDP, EDPHP and CDP were analyzed in positive ionization mode and
169 DPHP was analyzed in both negative and positive ionization mode.

170 ***Quantification of TPHP and DPHP in indoor dust***

171 Quantification of TPHP and DPHP in indoor dust was performed using the *quantitative*
172 *analysis MassHunter workstation* software from Agilent Technologies and using their
173 respective deuterated internal standards. The method was evaluated based on extraction
174 efficiency, clean-up losses, matrix effects and reproducibility.

175 For TPHP and DPHP, the instrument linear range was 0.005-5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and 0.005-10
176 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively. The instrument LOD and LOQ (TPHP and DPHP) were 0.1 ng/mL and
177 5 ng/mL , respectively. Method LOD and LOQ were calculated based on a signal-to-noise
178 ratio higher than 3 and 10, respectively, considering sample amount, final extract volume,
179 and total recovery. The estimated method LOD and LOQ for TPHP were 1.54 ng/g and 73.96
180 ng/g , respectively. For DPHP, the estimated method LOD and LOQ were 0.38 ng/g and 19.23
181 ng/g , respectively.

182 ***Statistics***

183 One-way ANOVA was employed to investigate if the TPHP and DPHP concentrations were
184 significantly different in dust collected in Spain and in the Netherlands as well as in dust
185 collected from different microenvironments. Pearson correlation was performed in order to
186 investigate the correlation between TPHP and DPHP in indoor dust (data was normally
187 distributed, after logarithmic transformation, Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test). For the
188 statistical calculations, the microenvironments were divided into four groups: floor dust
189 (bedrooms, living rooms and offices), dust collected from the surface of electronic
190 equipment, car dust and dust from the floors of public microenvironments.

191 ***Screening of aryl-phosphate flame retardants***

192 Target screening of aryl-PFRs was performed using the *quantitative analysis MassHunter*
193 *workstation* software from Agilent Technologies, namely CDP, RDP, EDPHP, IDP and BDP.

194 The main ion $[M+H]^+$ as well as two abundant fragment ions for each target compound were
195 selected. Criteria used for positives were signal-to-noise ratio above 3 and qualifier ratio
196 within 80-120% range of the ratio observed from injected authentic standards.

197 Instrumental LODs of these compounds were calculated from the analysis of authentic
198 standards (0.0001-10 ng/mL) and considering peak areas of $S/N \geq 3$. Method LODs were
199 estimated from instrumental LODs taking into account the concentration factor of the method
200 (sample size of 50 mg and final extract volume of 200 μ L) and considering 100% total
201 recovery and were 8 ng/g for RDP, 20 ng/g for EDPHP and IDP and 40 ng/g for CDP and
202 BDP.

203 **3. Results and discussion**

204 **3.1. Method optimization and validation**

205 The method for quantification of TPHP and DPHP in indoor dust was evaluated based on
206 extraction recovery (%), clean-up recoveries (%), matrix effects (%), and reproducibility
207 (RSD%) by using the indoor dust reference material SRM 2585 (50 mg). Since the material
208 already contained TPHP and DPHP at relatively high concentrations, the deuterated internal
209 standards (IS) were employed for recovery optimization. The reference material was spiked
210 in triplicates with 0.1 μ g IS (TPHP- d_{15} and DPHP- d_{10}). The spiking was done before
211 extraction, before clean-up or at the final reconstitution step in order to assess the extraction
212 efficiency, clean-up losses, matrix effects and total recoveries. When spiked before
213 extraction, the SRM was left stand for 2 h to allow the solvent to evaporate in order to mimic
214 as much as possible the interaction of the compound with the dust matrix.

215 The extraction of TPHP and DPHP from spiked SRM was performed by salting-out
216 extraction with acetonitrile and 3 M aqueous NH_4Ac as described in section 2.3. A two-phase
217 system was used to reduce co-extraction of unwanted matrix components and thus to achieve

218 cleaner extracts. After extraction, due to the complexity of the dust matrix, a clean-up step
219 with QuEChERS (75 mg MgSO₄, 25 mg PSA, 25 mg C₁₈, 25 mg GCB) was assessed. For
220 TPHP, signal suppression due to matrix was significant and the signal improved from 13±2%
221 to 29±5% when clean-up was utilized following the salting-out extraction with acetonitrile
222 and 3 M aqueous NH₄Ac. For DPHP, the matrix effects were lower when analyzed in the
223 negative ionization mode (87±2%) compared to the positive ionization mode (62±1%) so that
224 negative ionization was selected for further experiments. The extraction recoveries for TPHP
225 and DPHP were 92±19% and 79±3%, respectively and the clean-up recoveries were 91±6%
226 and 100±7% for TPHP and DPHP, respectively. Total recoveries (extraction + clean-up +
227 matrix effects) for TPHP and DPHP based on triplicate spiking experiments were 24±5% and
228 69±2%, respectively, and losses are expected to be well compensated by their deuterated IS.

229 Although concentrations of aryl-PFRs are not certified in SRM 2585, TPHP has been
230 reported by other authors ranging 980±60³¹ to 1110±48.⁶¹ The observed average
231 concentration of TPHP and DPHP in SRM 2585 (*n*=3) were 1075±151 ng/g and 4967±129
232 ng/g, respectively, which for TPHP is in accordance with previously reported concentrations.
233 In this sense, despite the low total recoveries of TPHP (mainly due to matrix effects), the
234 method worked properly for the quantitation of TPHP and matrix effects were compensated
235 by the deuterated internal standard. Matrix effects did not change drastically between
236 samples. The total recovery in the real dust samples were 28±12% (mean 25%) for TPHP and
237 101±21% (mean 101%) for DPHP, respectively.

238 **3.2 TPHP and DPHP concentrations in indoor dust**

239 TPHP and DPHP were detected at high concentrations in all samples analyzed from the
240 Netherlands and from Spain (Table 1). The highest concentrations of both TPHP and DPHP
241 were observed in dust samples collected from the seats and dashboards of cars (142,459 ng/g
242 and 79,661 ng/g for TPHP and DPHP, respectively) followed by dust collected from on top

243 of electronic equipment (45,330 ng/g and 21,899 ng/g for TPHP and DPHP, respectively). To
244 the best of our knowledge, only one study has reported DPHP in indoor dust in the range 75-
245 190 ng/g.⁵³ In general, TPHP levels were higher than the DPHP levels, commonly 2-3 times
246 higher, in some cases up to 90 times higher. However, in some samples ($n=14$) the
247 concentration of DPHP was up to 2-10 times higher than that of TPHP. These samples were
248 collected in different microenvironments and in both Spain and the Netherlands. This is also
249 the case of the reference material 2585 employed for the optimization and validation of the
250 method, which showed a DPHP concentration about five times higher than that of TPHP.
251 This could be due to the presence of DPHP coming from the degradation of aryl-PFRs other
252 than TPHP or from other sources of contamination, such as consumer products containing
253 DPHP as an additive (e.g. paint or coatings).

254 The high concentrations of TPHP and DPHP found on top of electronic equipment in
255 comparison to concentrations observed in dust collected from the floor in the same room
256 (Figure S-1) suggest that electronic equipment is a relevant source of TPHP and DPHP in the
257 indoor environment. Differences in contamination patterns between floor dust and dust from
258 elevated surfaces (electronics) should be also considered as a plausible cause. However, no
259 correlation was observed between the concentrations found in floor dust and in dust collected
260 from the surface of electronic equipment (TPHP, $r=0.18$; DPHP, $r=0.04$).

261 One-way ANOVA revealed that there was not a statistically significant difference between
262 TPHP and DPHP levels in dust collected in Spain and in the Netherlands (TPHP, $p=0.94$,
263 DPHP, $p=0.62$). The microenvironments were divided into four groups: floor dust (bedrooms,
264 living rooms and offices), dust collected on top of electronic equipment, car dust and dust
265 collected from the floors of public microenvironments. Among these groups, no statistically
266 significant difference in TPHP and DPHP levels were revealed except between car dust and
267 floor dust. The concentrations of TPHP and DPHP in car dust were significantly higher than

268 in floor dust ($p < 0.05$), which could be explained by high amounts of flame retardants being
 269 used in the manufacturing of car seats and dashboards and/or less frequently cleaning of cars
 270 in comparison to houses. Regarding the ratio of the median values of TPHP and DPHP (Table
 271 1), measured ranges were in the same order of magnitude (0.9-4.5 in Spain and 1.9-3.8 in the
 272 Netherlands).

273 **Table 1.** TPHP and DPHP detection frequency (DF) and concentrations (ng/g) in indoor dust
 274 from different microenvironments in Spain and the Netherlands.

		DF (%)	Mean \pm SD	Median	Min	Max	^a TPHPmedian/ DHPHmedian
TPHP (Spain)	Living rooms ($n=9$)	100	3161 \pm 6051	944	265	18912	4,5
	Bedrooms ($n=9$)	100	674 \pm 297	734	211	1094	3,7
	Offices ($n=4$)	100	760 \pm 413	637	412	1353	0,9
	On top of electronics ($n=13$)	100	5900 \pm 7105	2416	1270	26210	1,4
	Cars ($n=15$)	100	18305 \pm 36362	4441	762	142459	1,9
	Public microenvironments ($n=7$)	100	665 \pm 281	687	169	1004	1,9
DHPH (Spain)	Living rooms ($n=9$)	100	241 \pm 127	211	111	461	
	Bedrooms ($n=9$)	100	314 \pm 284	197	106	1031	
	Offices ($n=4$)	100	771 \pm 354	712	408	1251	
	On top of electronics ($n=13$)	100	3211 \pm 5780	1753	299	21899	
	Cars ($n=15$)	100	8294 \pm 19897	2311	923	79661	
	Public microenvironments ($n=7$)	100	371 \pm 103	357	263	556	
TPHP (The Netherlands)	Homes and offices ($n=12$)	100	3073 \pm 3789	1438	172	12853	1,9
	On top of electronics ($n=11$)	100	10353 \pm 12688	9786	285	45330	3,8
DHPH (The Netherlands)	Homes and offices ($n=12$)	100	1199 \pm 1227	742	151	4189	
	On top of electronics ($n=11$)	100	2781 \pm 2102	2581	218	6588	

275 ^aRatio of the median values of TPHP and DPHP in each microenvironment

276 The TPHP concentrations in indoor dust from homes in Spain and in the Netherlands are in
 277 line with those previously reported in Europe (Figure 1, Table S-2).^{8, 12, 15, 21, 24, 30, 31, 34} The
 278 same accounts for TPHP concentrations in dust collected from on top of electronic equipment
 279 as well as from floors of offices and public microenvironments (Figure 1, Table S-2).^{11, 12, 20,}
 280 ^{24, 30, 31, 34, 62} The median TPHP concentration observed in car dust (4,441 ng/g) was however
 281 somewhat higher than reported before (135-3,700 ng/g). Reported TPHP concentrations in
 282 house dust as well as in dust from other microenvironments span over a wide concentration

283 range (<2-1,798,000 ng/g) with the highest concentration reported being observed in house
 284 dust from the U.S.⁹ The lowest concentration was observed in house dust from Pakistan^{14, 16}
 285 and in car dust from Kuwait.¹⁶ This high variation in TPHP concentrations, spanning several
 286 orders of magnitude, may be explained by different fire-safety regulations in different
 287 countries as well as different regulations regarding the production and use of PBDEs.
 288 Variability between measurements due to the analytical challenges related to the analysis of
 289 aryl-PFRs should be also taken into account.⁶³

290
 291 **Figure 1. Reported median concentrations TPHP (ng/g) in indoor dust from houses (top)**
 292 **and from the surface of electronic equipment, offices, cars and public microenvironments**
 293 **(bottom) in this study and in other countries.**

294 **2.4. 3.3. Correlation between TPHP and DPHP in indoor dust**

295 Pearson correlation was performed to investigate the correlation between TPHP and
 296 DPHP concentrations in indoor dust. Taking into account all the samples collected from the

297 Netherlands and Spain ($n=80$), we observed a strong and statistically significant positive
298 correlation between the concentration of TPHP and DPHP in indoor dust ($r=0.90$, $p<0.01$)
299 (Figure 2).

300 Pearson correlation was also performed for individual microenvironments (Figure S-2).
301 Statistically significant positive correlations were observed in dust collected from floors of
302 houses and offices ($r=0.46$, $p<0.05$) (Figure S-2 A), on top of electronic equipment ($r=0.60$,
303 $p<0.01$) (Figure S-2 B) and cars ($r=0.99$, $p<0.01$) (Figure S-2 C). Positive correlation was
304 also observed in dust collected from public microenvironments ($r=0.69$) (Figure S-2 D),
305 however, not statistically significant ($p=0.12$). These findings suggest that the presence of
306 DPHP in indoor dust may be related to the presence of TPHP as an impurity and/or as *ong*
307 *diet, indoor dust inhalation and dermal contact with contaminated dust or products, being*
308 *the latter the more recently discussed in the literatua* degradation product. However, it cannot
309 be ruled out that the presence of DPHP in indoor dust might also be a result of degradation of
310 other aryl-PFRs or to its use as product additive. Chemical hydrolysis, photodegradation or
311 biodegradation may play a role with different magnitude in each microenvironment. The ratio
312 of TPHP to DPHP in the different microenvironments were in the range 0.09-89.68. One-way
313 ANOVA revealed that there were no statistically significant difference in the TPHP-DPHP
314 ratio between the different microenvironments ($p=0.82$) or between dust collected in Spain
315 and in the Netherlands ($p=0.54$).

317

318 *Figure 2. Pearson correlation between TPHP and DPHP concentration in different*
 319 *microenvironments in indoor dust from Spain (ES) and the Netherlands (NL), $r=0.90$,*
 320 *$p<0.01$.*

321

322 **3.4. Human exposure to TPHP and DPHP via indoor dust ingestion**

323 Human exposure scenarios to TPHP and DPHP via dust ingestion in Spain were
 324 estimated using a method based on that described by Abdallah and Covaci.¹⁸ Briefly, average
 325 and high dust ingestion rates (95th percentile) for adults (2.6 mg/day and 8.6 mg/day,
 326 respectively) and toddlers (41 mg/day and 140 mg/day, respectively)⁶⁴ were used to calculate
 327 an average and a worst-case scenario exposure to TPHP and DPHP via indoor dust.
 328 Estimated exposure scenarios were calculated based on median and maximum concentrations
 329 in indoor dust in homes (bedrooms and living rooms), offices, cars and public

330 microenvironments (different stores and one cafeteria) in Spain, taking into account the time
331 spent in each environment according to the typical human activity patterns described by
332 Abdallah and Covaci¹⁸ (i.e. for adults 63.8% home, 22.3% office, 5.1% Public
333 microenvironments, 4.1% car and 4.7% outdoors, and for toddlers 86.1% home, 5.1% Public
334 microenvironments, 4.1% car and 4.7% outdoors). Occupational exposure of drivers (e.g.
335 taxi drivers and truck drivers) were estimated by using the concentrations in cars as
336 representative concentrations for the working environment (i.e. time fraction spent in car was
337 26.4%).

338 The estimated exposure to TPHP and DPHP for different exposure scenarios including
339 workers (offices), drivers, non-workers and stay-home toddlers are illustrated in Figure 3.
340 The estimated daily exposure based on average dust ingestion rates and median
341 concentrations are in line with those reported elsewhere which are in the range 0.9-58.5
342 ng/day, 7.0-30.2 ng/day and 3-75.4 ng/day for adult workers, non-workers and stay-home
343 toddlers, respectively (Table S-3).^{12, 13, 15, 17, 18, 32-34}

344 For adults, the calculated worst-case scenario exposure estimates are in line with those
345 reported elsewhere (based on high dust ingestion rate and 95th percentile or maximum
346 concentration) which are in the range 13.0-953.2 ng/day and 70.0-506.1 ng/day for workers
347 and non-workers, respectively (Table S-3).^{12, 13, 15, 17, 18, 32-34} However, the worst-case scenario
348 estimated daily exposure to TPHP via dust ingestion for stay-home toddlers was 3104.5
349 ng/day, a value that is higher than those reported in previous studies (Table S-3). Despite the
350 high estimated daily exposure for toddlers, all calculated exposure estimates for different
351 scenarios are far below the reference dose of 164,500 ng/day (adults) and 28,905 ng/day
352 (toddlers) calculated from the lowest reported chronic NOAEL, 23.5 mg/kg/day⁶⁵ divided by
353 a safety factor of 10,000 and assuming body weights of 70 kg and 12.3 kg for adults and
354 toddlers, respectively according to US EPA.⁶⁶ To the best of our knowledge, this is the first

355 study to report estimated daily exposure scenarios to DPHP via indoor dust ingestion. It is
 356 worth mentioning that this is only one of identified the major routes of human exposure to
 357 flame retardants, among diet, indoor air inhalation and dermal contact with contaminated dust
 358 or products, being the latter the more recently discussed in the literature.
 359

360
 361 **Figure 3. Estimated daily intake (ng/day) for different exposure scenarios in Spain. TPHP**
 362 **and DPHP exposure scenarios are estimated based on average dust ingestion rates and**
 363 **median concentrations measured in indoor dust. Worst-case scenarios are estimated based**
 364 **on high dust ingestion rates and maximum concentrations observed in indoor dust.**
 365 **Reference doses for adults and toddlers are calculated from the lowest reported chronic**
 366 **NOAEL, 23.5 mg/kg/day⁶⁵ divided by a safety factor of 10,000 and assuming body weights**
 367 **of 70 kg and 12.3 kg for adults and toddlers, respectively.**

368

369 3.5 Estimated urinary levels of DPHP via indoor dust ingestion

370 Estimated urinary levels of DPHP as a result of exposure to TPHP and DPHP via indoor
 371 dust were calculated based on the median and maximum levels of TPHP and DPHP in indoor
 372 dust in Spain (country for which the sample size was higher and more diverse in terms of
 373 microenvironments). The time fractions spent in each microenvironment were also taken into

374 account according to the typical human activity patterns described in the previous section. A
375 method based on that described by Van den Eede et al.⁵³ was employed. Briefly, an average
376 and a high dust ingestion rate (95th percentile) for adults (2.6 mg/day and 8.6 mg/day) and
377 toddlers (41 mg/day and 140 mg/day)⁶⁴ were assumed. Other assumptions were the complete
378 absorption of TPHP and DPHP after dust ingestion as well as the complete excretion of
379 DPHP in urine and that DPHP is absorbed and excreted unchanged.⁶⁷ The assumption that
380 TPHP is metabolized into DPHP by liver enzymes at a rate of 20% was also included.⁶⁸
381 Based on these assumptions and assuming a mean urinary output of 800 mL/day for adults
382 and 600 mL/day for children, estimated DPHP urinary levels (ng/mL) were calculated for
383 different exposure scenarios in Spain including workers (offices), drivers, non-workers and
384 stay-home toddlers.

385 The estimated urinary DPHP levels as a result of exposure to TPHP and DPHP via indoor
386 dust ingestion (based on average dust ingestion rates and median concentrations) were 0.002
387 ng/mL, 0.004 ng/mL, 0.002 ng/mL and 0.032 ng/mL for adult workers, drivers, non-workers,
388 and stay-home toddlers, respectively (Table 2). These estimated urinary DPHP levels as a
389 result of exposure to TPHP and DPHP via indoor dust ingestion are not high enough to
390 explain the high DPHP urinary levels reported in the literature ranging <0.13-727 ng/mL.^{25,}
391 ⁴⁹⁻⁵⁴

392 The worst-case scenario urinary DPHP levels estimated for the different exposure scenarios
393 (based on high dust ingestion rate and maximum concentration in dust) were 0.085 ng/mL,
394 0.34 ng/mL, 0.094 ng/mL, and 2.011 ng/mL for workers (offices), drivers, non-workers and
395 stay-home toddlers, respectively (Table 2). The estimated urinary DPHP level in toddlers is
396 40 times higher than the worst-case scenario previously reported (0.05 ng/mL).⁵³
397 Furthermore, the estimated worst-case scenario urinary levels of DPHP are in the same range

398 as the lower urinary DPHP concentrations reported previously (<0.13 ng/mL),⁵⁴ however,
399 still inadequate to explain the high DPHP levels reported in urine.^{25, 49-54}

400 Van den Eede et al.⁶⁹ showed that serum enzymes are involved in the transformation of TPHP
401 into DPHP and that the amount TPHP that reaches the liver after intake may be strongly
402 reduced. Therefore, the metabolic transformation rate of TPHP into DPHP (by serum and
403 liver enzymes) could be higher than 20% resulting in an underestimation of urinary DPHP
404 levels. The same study also investigated the hydrolysis products of EDPHP by serum
405 enzymes and results suggest an additional production of DPHP from EDPHP, however, at a
406 much lower rate than for TPHP.

407 It should be noted that the TPHP and DPHP concentrations in indoor dust vary over
408 several orders of magnitude between different environments and that the estimated urinary
409 DPHP levels cannot be compared directly to reported urinary levels elsewhere without a large
410 degree of uncertainty. Furthermore, it should be taken into account that higher urinary levels
411 could be reached via dust ingestion since the excretion of DPHP would reach a peak only at a
412 certain time after ingestion depending on the kinetics of DPHP excretion via urine.
413 Additionally other exposure routes than dust ingestion should be considered since according
414 to recent studies dermal contact with contaminated dust seems to be a major exposure route
415 for aryl-PFRs and concentrations of TPHP in handwipes were associated with concentrations
416 of urine metabolites.^{70,71}

417

418

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420

421 **Table 2.** Estimated urinary DPHP concentration (ng/mL) for different exposure scenarios in
422 Spain.

	Average ingestion rate		High ingestion rate	
	Median	Maximum	Median	Maximum
Workers	0.002	0.026	0.006	0.085
Drivers	0.004	0.103	0.012	0.340
Non-workers	0.002	0.028	0.005	0.093
Stay-home toddlers	0.032	0.589	0.109	2.011

423

424 **3.6. Screening of aryl-PFRs in indoor dust**

425 TPHP and DPHP were detected in all samples analyzed from Spain ($n=57$) and the
426 Netherlands ($n=23$). Other aryl-PFRs, namely CDP, RDP, EDPHP, IDP and BDP were all
427 detected in indoor dust, however, with lower frequency (Table 3).

428 EDPHP was the most frequently detected aryl-PFR after TPHP and DPHP with a detection
429 frequency of 64.9% and 65.2% in Spain and the Netherlands, respectively, followed by IDP
430 (50.9% and 43.5%), BDP (33.3% and 34.8%), CDP (3.5% and 8.7%) and RDP (0% and
431 4.3%). Due to strong matrix effects and the lack of suitable internal standards for these
432 compounds they were not quantified. Detection frequencies of all aryl-PFRs included in the
433 present study were similar in samples collected from Spain and the Netherlands (Table S-4).

434 We should point out that not all possible aryl-PFRs were screened in this study, for example
435 isopropylated and tert-butylated triarylphosphate isomers (ITP and TBPP) were not included,
436 and they could also be related to DPHP.

437

438

439

440

441 **Table 3.** Compound name, CAS, molecular structure, chemical formula, monoisotopic mass
 442 and detection frequency (%) of TPHP, DPHP, CDP, IDP, EDPHP, RDP, and BDP in indoor
 443 dust from Spain and the Netherlands.

Compound CAS	Molecular structure	Chemical formula	Monoisotopic mass (g/mol)	Detection frequency (%)	
				Spain (<i>n</i> =57)	The Netherlands (<i>n</i> =23)
Triphenyl phosphate (TPHP) 115-86-6		C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₄ P	326.070801	100	100
Diphenyl phosphate (DPHP) 838-85-7		C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₄ P	250.039490	100	100
Cresyl diphenyl phosphate (CDP) 26444-49-5		C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₄ P	340.086456	3.5	8.7
Isodecyl diphenyl phosphate (IDP) 29761-21-5		C ₂₂ H ₃₁ O ₄ P	390.195984	50.9	43.5
2-Ethylhexyl diphenyl phosphate (EDPHP) 1241-94-7		C ₂₀ H ₂₇ O ₄ P	362.164703	64.9	65.2
Resorcinol bis(diphenyl phosphate) (RDP) 57583-54-7		C ₃₀ H ₂₄ O ₈ P ₂	574.094666	0	4.3
Bisphenol A bis(diphenyl phosphate) (BDP) 5945-33-5		C ₃₉ H ₃₄ O ₈ P ₂	692.172913	33.3	34.8

444

445 4. Conclusions

446 TPHP and DPHP were present at high concentrations with 100% detection frequency in all
 447 samples analyzed from Spain and the Netherlands. The highest maximum concentrations of

448 TPHP and DPHP were observed in dust collected from the seats and dashboards of cars
449 (142,459 ng/g and 79,661 ng/g for TPHP and DPHP, respectively), followed by dust
450 collected from the surface of electronic equipment (45,330 ng/g and 21,899 ng/g for TPHP
451 and DPHP, respectively). This suggests a high use of TPHP in the manufacturing of car
452 interiors and electronic equipment that are important contamination sources of this
453 compound. The lowest concentrations of TPHP (169 ng/g) and DPHP (106 ng/g) were
454 observed in floor dust collected from public microenvironments and bedrooms, respectively.

455 TPHP concentrations in house dust in Spain and the Netherlands are in line with those
456 reported in other European countries. The strong correlation between TPHP and DPHP levels
457 ($r=0.90$, $p<0.01$) suggests that TPHP could be a source for DPHP in indoor dust, probably as
458 a result of degradation. However, other possible sources for DPHP in indoor dust cannot be
459 ruled out since DPHP has been suggested to be an impurity, degradation product and
460 metabolite of some aryl-PFRs and it is used as a product additive. Indeed, other aryl-PFRs
461 were present in dust samples, namely CDP, IDP, EDPHP, RDP and BDP although less
462 frequently detected.

463 The estimated average daily exposure to TPHP and DPHP in Spain is highest for toddlers
464 (36.5 ng/g and 11.8 for TPHP and DPHP, respectively) followed by drivers (4.4 ng/g and 2.0
465 for TPHP and DPHP, respectively), which are both far below the reference dose for TPHP of
466 164,500 ng/day (adults) and 28,905 ng/day (toddlers). The estimated average urinary DPHP
467 concentrations as a result of exposure to TPHP and DPHP via indoor dust ingestion are far
468 below and insufficient to explain the high DPHP levels reported in urine. Only in the
469 estimated worst-case scenario, urinary DPHP concentrations are in the same range as the
470 lower reported DPHP levels. Other sources of TPHP exposure and/or the presence of other
471 aryl-PFRs that are degraded and/or metabolised into DPHP may be relevant sources to
472 explain the high concentrations of DPHP reported in urine.

473

474 **Conflict of interest**

475 The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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481

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